

**YORÙBÁ AND GLOBAL ACTIVISMS: THE CONTRIBUTION OF
WESTERN NIGERIA ARABIC SCHOLARS**

By

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Abstract

Arabic scholarsticism developed gradually from the native speakers to the Arabized North Africans. It spread afterwards to the Western Sudan, later known as West Africa, through proselytization of Islam, trade and commercial activities, as well as Sufi brotherhoods' propagation of their creeds. All these factors combined actually aided the entrenchment of Arabic culture among the indigenous people of West Africa, including the Yorubas, who occupied the South Western Nigeria and other parts of the neighbouring countries. Yoruba Activisms which cut across religious learning, did not exclude Yoruba Arabic activists who used the medium of Arabic language to express their feelings against slavery, colonialism, neo colonialization and expressed need for self rule, freedom of religion and fundamental human rights. This work therefore, examines the contributions of Yoruba Arabic scholars like Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori, Shaykh Muhammad al-Awwal Abdullahi Omupo and Shaykh Mustafa Zughlul al-Sunusi. Adopting qualitative and Chronological method of research. Their writings proved them as being part of Yoruba activism towards unfavourable behaviours of authorities during their contemporary ages.

Keywords: Activisms, Yoruba, Western Sudan, Culture , Arabic writings.

1.0 Introduction

Arabic language is one of the semitic class of languages that had flourished in the past and has networked its tentacles beyond its place of origin. Its only undoing is, its affiliation with a religion. Otherwise, it could be conveniently said that, it has parity with English, French and other leading languages of the world. However, despite its religious affiliation with Islam, the extent of its use

around the globe, its rich literature and adaptation of its alphabets to initialize writing of many other languages have made it a force in the literary world.

It may be added here that apart from Saudi-Arabia from where it originated, modern countries of the world like Iraq, Iran, Kuwait, Oman, Jordan, UAE, Egypt, Sudan and so on, have made Arabic one of their official languages, if not their lingual franca. Also, Arabic alphabets have been used to initialize writing of some Asian and African languages, before the coming of Europeans into these countries territories in the past. Prominent to us in Nigeria are Hausa and Yoruba languages. Such scripts are referred to as AJAMI writing, that is, writing Hausa and Yoruba languages, but using Arabic scripts. This, and many other factors made Arabic a popular means of expression and literary activities. In fact, when it is claimed that many tribes of Nigeria had become literate before the advent of colonial masters, Arabic was actually the means of literacy to them before the introduction of English language.

Yoruba Activism

Activism is the practice of using action to achieve a result, such as political demonstration or a strike in support of or in opposition to an issue.¹ An activist is defined as one who is politically active in the role of a citizen, especially, one who campaigns for change. Or, one who is conspicuously active in carrying out any occupational or professional functions. From the foregoing definitions, it may be clear to us, if we say there were in the past, or there are in the present, Arabic scholars who involved themselves in Yoruba activism towards achieving specific goals and aims. These Arabic scholars expressed their anger not only by carrying placards, but also through their writings, public preaching, indoctrination of their students and followers, and public condemnation of authorities and powers that be. While it is acknowledged that Yoruba activism are wide and dimensional, it is on record that Arabic scholars of Yoruba origin have contributed their own quota, and together with others have achieved their aims and objectives.

2.0 Arabic Language Mastery

It is unequivocal that Arabic language is foreign to us in Yoruba land. Our mother tongue is Yoruba which is written in alphabetical order, almost copied from the English language alphabets. Therefore, before anyone can become literate in

Arabic he needs to undergo a lot of training and retraining. In the past it seemed easier because a learner only dedicated himself to the rudiments of this language, and gradually achieved competency with time. He did not attend any other school to learn even his mother tongue (Yoruba) or English which later became our lingua franca. Such a learner became literate and can even write and put down his thoughts in Yoruba language in the form of Arabic characters. For example, the following Yoruba passage can be transcribed in Arabic thus:

Ewé ọsàn wéwé, ewé lààlì, koríko ọba,
eérú aláámó, a ó ẹ lágbo, a ó mú láàárò
lálé

Any Yoruba man literate in Arabic, but who could not read English or Yoruba will get the import of this fever solution dictated by a Yoruba elder. This was how literacy in Arabic sustained Hausa and Yoruba languages and cultures before the coming of Europeans.

2.1 Arabic as a Medium of Expression

Apart from the above practice, learners of Arabic gradually attained proficiency in the language and began to make use of it as a medium of expressing their feelings. Right from 180 C.E, when the likes of Shehu Uthman dan Fodio, Shaykh Abdullahi bn. Fodio, Sultan Muhammad bn. Dan Fodio and Shayph Muhammad El-kanemi started putting down their thoughts in Arabic, the practice later extended to Yoruba land where Arabic scholars literate in the language followed suit. Arabic as a medium started to be used as a means of expression of feelings among Yoruba scholars. Some of them engaged in public preaching, demonstrating Yoruba activism against colonization, subjugation, denial of freedom of religion and rampant conversion of their children and wards into Christianity through the introduction of Western education.

Some of them put their thoughts down in writing and sent these to their friends and students across Yoruba land. This later developed into formation of different groups with specific agitations and demands. For instance, early Yoruba Arabic scholars established local Arabic schools (Madrasah) under their watch, where students were not allowed to have access to western type of education and were groomed to recognize dangers inherent in acquiring this western education. Some

of these thoughts were put down in writing for posterity yet unborn. Arabic scholars like Shaykh Muhammad Tajul-Adab of Ilorin, Shaykh Yusuf Agbaji (Baba Lagbaji), Shaykh Abdus-Salam Bamidele (Baba Lamuniyah), Shaykh Usman Lanase, demonstrated Yoruba activism to a greater extent. They broke away from the larger society where they lived. They tried to form a society where pristine Islam could be practiced. They therefore introduced some practices like use of big turbans, veiling of their wives and daughters and restricting them to the four walls of their houses and growing and nurturing big beards. Not only did they practice these, they also rejected and condemned those who did not fall in line. They withdrew from use of all life modern facilities which they perceived as temptations that could draw them far from God. They became so active in these permutations that government and other authorities perceived them to be strange and different sets of people.¹

The next generation of Arabic scholars who were involved in Yoruba activism, but who chose different paths to show their aversion to the happenings in their environment, included Shaykh Kamalu-deen Al-Adabi, Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori (1917-1992), Shaykh Bisiriyu Apalara (1918-1953) (he was murdered for his activism and his remains never found),¹ Shaykh Ahmad Tijani Awelenje of Saki (1897-1967),¹ Shaykh Abdul-Baqi Muhammed (Akewukewe Oluko Agba of Iwo), Shaykh Salahudeen Olayiwola of Ede (d. 2017), Shaykh Abdul-Azeez Ajagbemokeferi and Shaykh Mustafa Zughlul al-Sunusi (founder of Daru Da'wah Arabic Institute, Isolo Lagos). Many of this category of scholars were perfect Arabic authors who used their erudition in Arabic to promote Yoruba activism in their respective chosen professions.

3.0 Involvement of Arabic Laureates in Yoruba Activism

Apart from the above mentioned eminent Arabic scholars whose involvements in Yoruba activism were not meager, either by their outspokenness or by their writings against the powers that be, others whose participation in the Yoruba activism cannot be over-emphasized include a group of activist who came up with the establishment of Islamic pressure groups which later got registered as Association Prominent in this group is Anwar-Ul-Islam, established in 1916. It was founded by a group of Arabic and Islamic activists who succeeded from Ahmadiyyah Movement.¹ This group was followed by the popular Ansar-Ud-

Deen Society of Nigeria, established in 1923. AUD, as popularly referred to, then was a Muslim pressure group established by some Yoruba Islamic activists for the purpose of “the educational development of Muslims and also as a body to enhance the moral and social development of the Muslim community in Lagos”.¹

The Muslim Students’ Society of Nigeria (MSSN) was founded in Lagos in 1954, by prominent Yoruba Islamic activists like Alhaj Dr. Lateef Adegbite (1933-2012). He was a former Attorney General of the Western Region of Nigeria, and later became Secretary General of the Nigerian Supreme Council of Nigeria. And Prof. Aliu Babatunde Fafunwa (1923-2010), who was the first Nigerian Professor of Education and later became Minister of Education, Federal Republic of Nigeria. The duo, through their moderate Yoruba activism, assisted Muslim youths against becoming militants in cause of fighting for their religions and educational rights.

The National Council of Muslim Youth Organisation (NACOMYO) was also formed in 1980 by prominent Arabic and Islamic scholars and Yoruba activists like, Prof. D.O.S. Noibi, Prof. S.H.A Malik, Prof. K.K. Oloso, Barrister A.R.A. Shittu among others to “bring all Muslim youth organization together, to jointly defend the cause of Islam and the rights of the Muslims in Nigeria.”¹ It should be put on record that Yoruba Arabic activists came up with the idea of forming NACOMYO because MSSN (Muslim Students’ Society of Nigeria) had its limits as a Students’ Union. NACOMYO had a broader line to operate in towns and cities and engage governments on issues that affect rights of Muslims and Islamic religion. The formation of NACOMYO, no doubt brought to limelight many Yoruba activists who were Arabic scholars.

As time passed by and the need to further defend the cause of Islam arose, some other group of Arabic and Islamic scholars cum activists felt the need to take Yoruba activism beyond student bodies or youth associations. Therefore, another idea of forming a broader Muslim group that would serve as a pressure group was mooted. The Muslim communities of each state were formed. There is no doubt that outspoken Yoruba Arabic activists in Western states led the groups in their respective states. For example, in Osun State, Shaykh Salahudeen Ade Olayiwola, a proprietor of Arabic Institute, Ede, was the pioneer President.

Further to the unrelenting posture of some of these Arabic Scholars, another wider and broader activism was birthed to embrace all western part of Nigeria. Muslim Ummah of South West Nigeria (MUSWEN) was officially inaugurated in Ibadan, Oyo State on Sunday 10th August, 2008. The vision of MUSWEN is for the body to serve as “a united and effective voice for Muslims in the region under a strong, veritable and collective leadership.”¹ The aim of this group is to “raise the profile of the Muslims of this part of Nigeria like enabling them and their offspring to live their lives fully as staunch believers and practioner of the faith while at the same time contributing their quota to the development of the country and as responsible and respected citizens”.¹ Prominent Yoruba Muslim activist behind the formation of this group are Prof. Aliu Babatunde Fafunwa, earlier mentioned in this work, Prof. Daud Shittu Noibi, formerly of the Department of Arabic, University of Ibadan, who later became President of the group.

The Muslim Right Concern (MURIC) was later formed by some Yoruba activists led by another Arabic and Islamic scholar, Prof. Ishaq Lakin Akintola of the Lagos State University, Ojoo. In recent times, this scholar, as leader of this group, reacts to every thorny issue in Nigeria. Sometimes, confronting the governments on issues of interests to Islam and Muslims. Writing treatises, reports, memoranda and documentation of such was part of activisms of this group. The group has become a sort of mouthpiece for the oppressed and marginalized Muslims in Yoruba land and Nigeria in general.

3.1 The Yoruba Arabic Scholars and their Participation in Yoruba Activisms

Many Arabic scholars of Yoruba extraction contributed their quota to Yoruba activisms through their scholarly writings, sermons, public preaching, and direct influence on their students and followers. Prominent among these are Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori, Shaykh Muhammad al-Awwal of Omupo and Shaykh Mustafa Zaghlul al-Sunusi.

Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori was born by an itinerant Arabic scholar of Ilorin origin in Benin Republic in 1917. Having acquired substantial knowledge of Arabic and Islamic culture, he became an activist in liberating Muslims from ignorance, illiteracy and oppression of the powers that be. He adopted three

principal methods in his activism methods. He set up Arabic training centres where he trained young minds to later join him in his crusade. Many Arabic scholars, who later became Yoruba activists actually passed through Shaykh Adam's tutelage. He also engaged in public preaching, where he spoke against human right abuses, oppression in religious practices and self-serving leaders who worked against the progress and development of the country.

More prominent in the approach of Shaykh Adam in Yoruba activism is his scholarly Arabic writings on topical issues bordering on human rights, religious guidance, freedom of expression and re-writing history. Describing him, Badmus O. Yusuf wrote:

In 1962, Adam fought tooth and nail in Lagos to make his stand known against an unpopular law which stipulated that permission be obtained before preaching ... It was in recognition of his outstanding scholarship that made Saudi Arabia government courtesy of the Muslim World League (MWL) requested him to translate the glorious Qur'an into the Yoruba language..

The scholarly contributions of Shaykh Adam Abdullahi Al-Ilori impacted many modern scholars from within and outside Nigeria.¹

Some of the Shaykh Adam's literary works that portray is activism include:

- Huququl-insani (Human Rights)
- Al-Islam Dinu wa Dawlah (Islam is Religion and Government)
- Aslu Qobail Yuruba (The Origin of Yoruba Tribes)
- Al-Islam fi Naijiriyya (Islam in Nigeria)
- Nasim saba (Morning Breeze)
- Nizam Ta'alimul-Arabi wal-Islami (System of Arabic and Islamic Teaching)

Another prominent Arabic scholar of Yoruba extraction who became known with his activism through literary (1926-2009) activities is Shaykh Muhammad al-Awwal of Omupo. He was born in Omupo Kwara State in 1926, and grew up in

Lagos where he acquired Arabic and Islamic knowledge from some Ilorin and Kano born scholars.¹ Prominent among his teachers are Shaykh Salahudeen Aniyalara, Shaykh Aminullahi Babala, Shaykh Umar Agbaji and Shaykh ‘Umar Abubakr Falke. Shaykh Muhammad al-Awwal was a mystic, he got initiated into the Tijaniyya brotherhood in 1941 and later met with the leader of Tijaniyyah in West Africa, a Senegalese Arabic activist and scholar, Shaykh Ibrahim Nyass. Under this teacher, he got very much influenced and learnt a lot of involvement in literary rendition and socio-political activisms. There are about twenty publications to his credit, which he wrote to influence his students and followers. He was a teacher with a well-established Arabic school, a Tijaniyyah leader with a very large followers, and a mentor to all people of his time. Some of his literary works, which he used to guide and influence his followers in Yoruba activisms include:

- Al-Harakat al-Tijaniyyah fi Naijiriyya
- Al-Istiqamah fi al-Islam
- Asbab wahadat al-Ummat al-Islamiyyah
- Al-Mafahim al-Tijaniyyah
- Mawridu Rida
- Sufnu al-Najat

Shaykh Mustafa Zughlul al-Sunusi (1938-2017) is another prominent Yoruba activist who used his mastery of Arabic to contribute in no small measure to Yoruba activisms. He was born in 1938 in Ikirun, South West Nigeria. He learnt Qur’an under his father and later joined the school of Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori in Agege Lagos. He became an Arabic scholar and a Yoruba activist under the tutelage of his teacher, Shaykh Adam Abdullahi al-Ilori. Shaykh Zughlul travelled to many Arab countries and got more influenced in socio-political happenings in those countries. He later established his own Arabic school at Isolo, Lagos and produced many other scholars and activists who followed his footsteps both in literary productions and Yoruba activisms.

Shaykh Mustafa Zughlul al-Sunusi through his Friday sermons, Ramadan Tafsir, public preaching and writings proved himself not only a scholar of repute but also a Yoruba activist who used his Arabic literary rendition to fight against human right oppression, government mal-administration and global aggression. He wrote

many books in Arabic on topical issues, one of which is *Saya'udul-Arab ila falastin*. In this collection, he criticized the state of Israel and their supporters for denying the people of Palestine to have a country of their own, and waging wars against the innocent of Gaza. He expressed hope that no matter the oppression and suppression, the Palestinian people, who have become refugees in other neighbouring countries shall one day return and have their land back as a nation of their own.

Not only in writing, but also in public preaching and conference paper presentation, he has demonstrated his activism. In one of his open lectures organized by Allahu-Samad Foundation of Nigeria (ASFON) in Lagos, he delivered a paper titled “*Gay-Marriage: the Islamic Perspective*”. Therein he expressed his displeasure and aversion to the worldly trends of legalizing gay-marriage by the America and other Western worlds.¹

He stated in his writing:

It is at this point that we commend the step taken by President Jonathan who signed into law the anti-gay/same sex marriage law which carried 14 years jail term for anyone found guilty of the offence. We also condemn all the Western nations that have joined in legalizing same sex marriage and its activities. We accept the fact that some of them were our colonial masters who we have shared development ideas on socio-political and economic situation together in the past, but on this issue, we are happy to be different. We should not be bothered by their threats after President Jonathan signed the anti-gay bill into law.¹

In his attribute to Shaykh Mustafa Zughlul al-Sunusi, one of his former students and a University Don, Saheed Ahmad Rufai compared him to Prof. Abiola Irele, a literary giant of French African Literature. In his writing titled “*Of Abiola Irele and Mustapha Zugloul: An Evaluative Engagement with Two Literary Traditions*”. Rufai stated:

Nigeria currently mourns two literary giants of different traditions. One of them is Abiola Irele, renowned Professor of French and African Literature and the other, Shaykh Mustapha Zuglul, a world-class and arguably the most prolific traditional Arabic literary writer in South Western Nigeria, after Shaykh Al-Iluriyy.¹

Apart from his renowned Arabic book on Palestine, Shaykh Mustapha Zughlul al-Sunusi had six other literary works to his credit in Arabic and revolutionary discourse in Arabic language.

With daily developments in reactions and counter reactions to socio-political and socio-cultural activities around the globe, it is expected that different forms and styles of activism from among the Yoruba people of Western Nigeria will continue to grow. And as long as this is the case, more Arabic scholars will no longer sit on the fence, but rather participate in expressing their feelings through writings and public discourses.

Modern trends among Arabic scholars, as far as Yoruba activism is concerned have shown that the future of Arabic literarism is bright. A professor of Arabic/Islamic studies, Prof. Ishaq Lakin Akintola is at head of a group called Muslim Right Concern (MURIC), and educating Muslims and fighting for their rights are part of their objectives. In more recent time also, social media has been awashed with a large number of Arabic scholars who have turned to Yoruba human right agitators and Yoruba activists using the medium of Arabic scholars like Alh. Muideen Ajani Bello, a missionary of Ansar-Ud-Deen Society of Nigeria, Shaykh Muideen Salman Hussain, the Chief Imam of Offa and others numerous to mentioned have displayed their Yoruba activism through the use of Arabic language on the internet.

5.0 Conclusion

From the foregoing, it has been established that the Yoruba activism is not limited to only Yoruba traditionalists or educated Yoruba fellows in Western oriented schools, but rather, we have seen the contributions of the Yoruba Arabic scholars who have made use of their literary competence in other languages of the world,

like Arabic, especially in their public presentations, preachings, sermons and literary renditions. The more their incoming students and fellows acquire better competency in the language, the better their contributions to their overall influence for good in our society.

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